

Lasers In Dental Implantology : A New Era of Precision And Healing

Jaspreet Singh Khurana¹, Neelu Verma², Shipra Singh³, Farzana Wasi⁴

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PG Student¹
Department of Periodontology
Career Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences & Hospital
Lucknow

Reader²
Department of Periodontology,
Career Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences & Hospital
Lucknow

PG Student³
Department of Periodontology
Career Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences & Hospital
Lucknow

PG Student⁴
Department of Periodontology
Career Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences & Hospital
Lucknow

Abstract

In recent decades, dental implantology has emerged as a therapy approach with a high rate of acceptability and success. In 1989, lasers were first used in clinical dentistry in an effort to address some of the issues with traditional dental practices. Over the past few years, their application in implant dentistry has increased. Lasers can especially be useful in dealing with complications from implant therapy and treatment of peri-implantitis. This article aims to provide an understanding of lasers with different wavelengths for specific dental implant situations and to describe the characteristics, merits and demerits and clinical applications.

Keywords: Lasers, Dental implants, Peri-implantitis

Introduction

Laser technology has significantly advanced the field of implant dentistry, offering a range of benefits that enhance both the efficiency and precision of treatments. In recent years, lasers have become increasingly popular for various dental procedures, including implant placement, soft tissue management, and bone healing. By harnessing focused light energy, lasers allow for minimally invasive techniques that reduce patient discomfort, promote faster recovery, and improve the overall success rates of implants. In the field of dentistry, laser can be used for various surgical and nonsurgical procedures since its introduction by Maiman in 1960. The carbon dioxide (CO₂) laser has been used in oral and maxillofacial surgery since its development in 1964. Lasers were brought to general practice in 1989 by Drs. William and Terry Myers² who modified an ophthalmic Nd:YAG laser for dental use. This unit (dLase 300, American Dental Laser, Southfield, Michigan) pioneered the development of lasers dedicated to the field of dentistry rather than medicine. In 1985, the publication of Tissue Integrated Prostheses: Osseointegration in Clinical Dentistry by Branemark et al ushered in the era of osseointegration.

In this regard, laser technology not only enhances conventional techniques but also offers new solutions to commonly encountered issues in implant dentistry. Lasers are revolutionizing the placement of dental implants, whether for tissue cutting, disinfection, or bone development stimulation, assuring more consistent and efficient results for patients. Depending on the range of wavelengths and the simultaneous absorption by biological chromophores, OMFS uses a variety of laser types. Increased hemostasis, better visualization of the surgical site, less injury to the surrounding tissue, reduced swelling, and a decreased risk of infection due to the photosterilization effect are some benefits of employing lasers in implant dentistry. The use of lasers depends on the situation to which it is applied and the particular wavelength suitable for that.

Light Amplification Of Stimulated Emission Radiation(laser):

A device that transforms light of various frequencies into an intense, small, and nearly non divergent beam of monochromatic radiation within the visible range.³

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Laser - Tissue Interaction

Lasers have four types of interactions with the target tissue which depends on the optical properties of that tissue: Absorption, transmission of laser energy, reflection and scattering of the laser light. (Fig-1)

In relation to implant dentistry lasers have various advantages including increased hemostasis, improved visibility of surgical site, minimal damage to the surrounding tissue, reduced swelling, and decreased infection due to photo sterilization effect and in turn less pain postoperatively.

The use of lasers depends on the situation to which it is applied and the particular wavelength suitable for that. The clinical application of lasers can be broadly categorized into two modalities: nonsurgical use (laser-welded titanium framework technology, laser micropatterning of dental implants, computer-assisted laser-cured surgical template, and laser-oriented recording on dental prostheses) and surgical use (removal of granulation tissue, biomodulation, implant placement, second-stage recovery and gingival management, treatment of peri-implantitis, and low-level laser therapy [LLL]).

Classification of Laser

A. According To Light Spectrum⁵

Spectrum	Wavelength	Applications
U.V Light	100nm-400nm	Not used in dentistry
Visible Light	400nm-750nm	Most commonly used in dentistry (argon & diagnodent laser)
Infrared Light	750nm-10000nm	Most dental lasers are in this spectrum

B. According To Material Used⁵

Gas	Liquid	Solid
Carbon dioxide	Not so far in clinical use	Diodes,Nd:YAG,Er:YAG, Er,Cr:YSGG

C. Laser Wavelengths And Their Benefits In Clinical Implant Dentistry⁶

Laser Systems	Wavelength	Application	Benefits
Diode	810 or 980nm	Soft tissues	++
Nd:YAG	1640nm	Soft tissues	+
Er:YAG	2940nm	Hard tissues	+++
Er:YAG	2940nm	Soft tissues	+
CO ₂	10,600nm	Soft tissues	++++

Application Of Laser In Dental Implants

a. Laser-welded Titanium Framework Technology

Laser-welded technology is considered as an alternative to the conventional lost wax-casting technique in the field of implant dentistry. The titanium has various characteristics that are advantageous for its use in bar superstructures. In addition to this, laser energy allows for a much stronger, passively fitting superstructure.⁷

b. Laser Micropatterning of Dental Implants

Laser peening is a form of cold working, produces a surface with refined grain structures, compressive residual stresses, and increased hardness in metallic materials.⁸ It is performed using precision laser micromachining (excimers or Nd:YAG laser) on implant surface, which creates a controlled surface roughness and has shown to stimulate bone growth at the surface. (Fig 2)

Fig 2: Considering the value of 3D cultures for enhancing the understanding the adhesion, Proliferation, and Osteogenesis on Titanium Dental Implants

a. Computer-aided Laser Cured Surgical Template

Guided implant placement offers superior precision and control relative to freehand insertion. Physical models can be created using rapid prototyping techniques based on virtual computational models. The various rapid prototyping technologies that are currently in use are stereolithography (SLA), inkjet-based system (three dimensional printing), selective laser sintering (SLS), and fused deposition modeling, of which the SLA uses an ultraviolet laser to “laser cure” cross sections of a liquid resin. SLS models are opaque as compared to SLA ones that are translucent.⁹

b. Laser-Assisted Osteotomy

The effects of laser on the bone ablation and in general the use of lasers for traditional osteotomies have been examined. The usage of drills has caused patients concern and suffering. Handpieces, bone files, and other tools have been employed in bone removal techniques for a long time. When using lasers to remove bone, no pressure needs to be applied, which may be advantageous when doing an osteotomy. Numerous researchers have proven that the Er:YAG laser

can cut bone precisely while causing the least amount of heat damage.

A study by Kesler et al¹⁰ has shown Er:YAG to be a safe option for use in osteotomy procedures. Keller et al found a slower recovery time and tissue healing after laser osteotomy in rabbits. During osteotomy procedures, an increase in temperature of the bone increases the risk for developing postoperative complications. Possibility of overheating the bone is high when conventional drill systems are used due to difficulty in getting the coolant between the drill and the bone.

c. Laser Assisted Implant placement

Minimally invasive implant placement, using the tissue punch method, has become a popular way to place implants when proper bone height and width are available. Hard tissue lasers like Er: YAG can be used to obtain the initial breach for implant placement rather than using micromotor. A laser is used to remove the soft tissue, and the cortical plate of bone in a circular pattern to approximately 2–3 mm and rest of the osteotomy site can be prepared using a handpiece drill. Unlike conventional drills, the laser tip has less tendency to slip. This leads to quick healing time, fast integration, minimal patient discomfort, and superior bone-to-implant contact. This also eliminates the need for trauma during flap elevation and suture placement.¹¹

d. Use of Laser Irradiation to Accelerate Osseointegration

The ultimate and the most ideal result desired after implant placement is osseointegration. Osteoblast attachment to the surface of the titanium implants is important for new bone formation and better implant healing. This has been extensively studied, and constant efforts are made to improve the integration of the implant at the surrounding bone. Lasers are being investigated for possibly improving osseointegration.

Kesler et al¹⁰ have shown that use of laser has improved osseointegration around titanium implants when compared with traditional osteotomies. It was also reported that healing rate was almost comparative for both Er:YAG laser and bur drilling.

e. Use of Laser as a Hemostatic Tool

There are a large number of patients receiving implants, who are on long term anticoagulant therapy or other systemic medical problems and could benefit from a quick and effective hemostasis; therefore, the use of laser in this aspect is being evaluated especially for better blood clot stabilization in the surgical site. In a study by Ackermann¹², an Nd: YAG laser was applied with a handpiece and was deemed effective in bringing about hemostasis.

f. Uncovering Implants in the Second Stage

The different wavelengths of laser can be used to uncover implants in stage-II implant surgery. The most commonly used lasers in this case are the CO₂ lasers, and Er:YAG

lasers are used with success, whereas Nd:YAG laser is contraindicated as this causes temperature buildup around the implants and also melting of the implant surface. Laser treated tissue margins do not recede after healing.

g. Peri-Implantitis Management¹⁷

Peri-Implantitis is a rapidly progressive failure of osseointegration, and there is the production of bacterial toxins that lead to inflammatory changes and bone loss. In the case of peri-implantitis, the implant surface is contaminated with soft tissue cells, bacteria and other bacterial by-products. Complete removal of endotoxins and bacterial plaque between implant threads with mechanical instruments is challenging. A laser wavelength that is safe to bone can be used to degranulate and debride the compromised implant surfaces. It has been demonstrated that Er: YAG, CO₂ lasers, and diode lasers may all efficiently remove calculus and plaque from implant abutments without causing surface damage. Nd: YAG lasers even with their excellent sterilization qualities are contraindicated for use in the treatment of peri-implantitis as they cause an increase in the surface temperature and also changes of the implant surface.

h. Lasers to Repair Ailing Implants

One of the most interesting uses of lasers in implant dentistry is the possibility of salvaging compromised implants by decontaminating their surfaces with laser energy. A number of clinical studies have been done to examine how, when, and whether lasers can be used successfully to help these situations. Diode lasers were used in a study by Bach et al who found a significant improvement in the 5-year survival rate when integrating laser decontamination into the approved treatment protocol.

Advantages¹⁸

The advantages of using lasers in implant dentistry are the same as for any other soft tissue dental procedure. These advantages include increased hemostasis, minimal damage to the surrounding tissue, reduced swelling, reduced infection, and reduced pain postoperatively. Due to the hemostasis provided by lasers, there is the significant advantage of improved visibility during surgery. The increasing popularity of the erbium family of lasers, with their hard tissue ablation capability, has added the potential for its use for osteotomy and decontamination of infected and ailing implant bodies. In general, the laser gives therapists numerous advantages over classical surgical interventions, including

- Faster recovery
- Reduced chance of infection
- Decreased sensitivity
- Reduced number of visits after oral surgery
- Shortened intervention time
- Less postoperative pain
- Less bleeding

- Accelerated bone healing

Conclusion

The incorporation of laser technology into laser implant technology has broadened the scope of available treatment modalities, offering clinician more precise, effective and minimally invasive solutions. From pre-surgical planning and implant site preparation to second-stage recovery ,soft tissue management and implant surface decontamination, laser have proven valuable across various clinical applications. Furthermore, evidence based use of specific laser wavelengths promises to enhance both therapeutic outcomes and patient experiences, contributing to safer, quicker and more predictable implant procedures.

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